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FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT OF ANTIMICROBIAL ZINC OXIDE NANOPARTICLE LOADED TRANS DERMAL PATCH BY USING 2³ FACTORIAL DESIGN.

Sagar Kothawade^{1*}, Udhhav Bagul¹, Chandrakant Kokare¹, Shubhangee Giikwad¹, Rutuja Wakure¹, Shubham Biyani², Chetan Harne¹

¹STES, Sinhgad Institute of Pharmacy, Narhe, Pune (MH), 411041, India.

²School of Pharmacy S.R.T.M University, Nanded (MH), 431606, India.

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ABSTRACT

Inorganic metal oxide nanoparticles are well known for significant antimicrobial activity. The zinc oxide nanoparticles have potential to act as antimicrobial agent in microbial infections due to its unique properties. Zinc oxide nanoparticles prefer as an alternative for antibiotics. It having shorter half-life and poor bioavailability. In the present work, the Trans dermal patch of zinc oxide nanoparticles were prepared to extended the release as well as improve bioavailability. The Trans dermal patch was prepared by solvent evaporation method. The preliminary trial batches were formulated with different polymer viz. HPMC E15, HPMC E5, HPMC E3, sodium alginate, along with plasticizer used as PEG. The prepared batches were evaluated for weight variation, thickness, Folding endurance, tensile strength, Moisture content, and *in-vitro* drug release. Amongst all five formulation batches, batch no A4 containing HPMC E5 and PEG 20% of formulation has shown thickness 0.312, folding endurance 340-fold along with 100% drug release within 12 hrs. The compatibility study of drug and excipients was carried out by FT-IR spectroscopy. Based on the results, the batch No A4 was selected for optimization by 2³ factorial designs. Optimised batch was evaluated for various parameter thickness weight variations, folding endurance, tensile strength, *In-vitro* % drug release. Optimised batch was subjected for stability studies were found to be stable. To avoid first pass metabolism and improve the bioavailability ZnO NPs is having promising antimicrobial agent and it can be formulated in transdermal patches for treatment of microbial infection.

Corresponding author

Sagar Kothawade

Department of Pharmaceutics,
STES, Sinhgad Institute of Pharmacy,
Narhe, Pune, Maharashtra, India, 411041.
sagarwani560@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Zinc oxide nanoparticles exhibit strong antimicrobial activity. But it has some drawbacks such as less solubility as well as possesses GI irritation. The oral administration of ZnO NP poor bioavailability due to first-pass metabolism. Hence, in order to avoid these drawbacks, the present work involves synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles. Moreover, ZnO nanoparticles loaded transdermal patches developed to facilitate absorption and utilize their antimicrobial potency [1-2].

Transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) means a route of delivery of drug through the skin to gain local or systemic therapeutic action. It is one of the major areas of research for the third-generation pharmaceutical preparations, next only to oral medication and injection [3]. The advantages of use of this route as administration route of the drug is, convenience, easy to use, non-invasive and it also improves patient compliance. It reduces the fluctuation of the concentration of drug in the blood and therefore, steady plasma levels can be achieved through this route. It also involves easy detection of drug and less chances of overdose. At the same time, it avoids the gastrointestinal environment, such as pH, enzymatic activity, interference of drug and food on the drug efficacy and first pass effect by liver. These conditions prolong the therapeutic effect of drugs with shorter half-life and longer drug stability [4]. Drug administration can be stopped if required by simply removing the patch from site. [5]. When drugs are delivered through the skin it is difficult to achieve adequate permeability rate as per therapeutic requirements, to overcome these difficulties nanotechnology may be a good choice [6-7]. A transdermal patch is a medicated adhesive patch which is to be placed on skin to deliver a specific dose of medication through epidermis into the bloodstream [8]. This could even help in healing of an injured area of the body. Transdermal patch having better patient compliance than painful parenteral injection. The suitable candidate for transdermal patch is those drugs having lipophilic nature, low molecular weight, and small daily dose [9].

The infectious diseases are a major threat to public health worldwide. The microbial strains resistant to antimicrobials now have become a serious problem that increases the need to develop new antimicrobial materials [10]. The nanotechnology is the area which has created many new antimicrobial options. This is group of materials with completely different properties in comparison with their bulk materials [11]. The larger surface area of nanoparticles due to their smaller size increases the possibility of more interaction with microbial cell membrane resulting strong agent against harmful microbes [12].

The aim and objective of the present study is to assess the particle size of previously synthesized Zinc oxide nanoparticles via particle size analyser along with antimicrobial activity by well diffusion method [13]. Furthermore, transdermal patch loaded with Zinc oxide nanoparticles was formulated. This patch then evaluated for mechanical strength and percentage drug release were performed with help of diffusion cell membrane apparatus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Zinc oxide nanoparticles which was prepared by Rutuja Wakure followed by co-precipitation method [14]. used in this study. Other materials i.e. HPMC E5, E3, E15, PEG was obtained as a gift sample from Aurobindo Research Centre Hyderabad. All chemicals used are of analytical grade.

Selection of Excipients

The concentration of each excipient was selected as per their maximum potency per dose of ingredient by referring the Handbook of pharmaceutical excipients [15]. and Inactive Ingredients Guidelines Limit

STUDY OF ZnO NPs

Solubility Study

An excess of Zinc oxide nanoparticles was added to various solvents such as 10 ml of distilled water, HCl, Phosphate buffer, methanol, DMSO and subjected to ultra-sonication for 24 hours at room temperature. The solution was then filtered through Whatman filter and after making suitable dilutions, the amount of drug dissolved in various solvents was analysed spectrophotometrically using UV spectrophotometer (UV-730, Jasco).

Construction of Calibration Curve for Zinc Oxide nanoparticles

Based on Preformulation solubility studies methanol was used for constructing the calibration curve of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles. The standard stock solution was diluted to obtain series of Zinc Oxide nanoparticles solution in the concentration range 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 µg/ml. The absorbance was measured by using UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Jasco 730) at 374 nm and the graph was plotted. This graph was used for estimation of drug release in the formulated transdermal patch of zinc oxide nanoparticles.

Antimicrobial Activity of ZnO NPs

Well- diffusion method was used to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of synthesized ZnO NPs. This was carried out by using both bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*) and fungi (*Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*) strains. The inoculum of strains was prepared by growing a single colony for 24hrs in nutrient broth. The prepared nutrient broth agar plates were seeded with microbial strains broth. Then 20 µl of synthesized ZnO NPs with concentration of 100 µg/ml was added in wells. Moreover, the plates were incubated at 37^oc for 48 hrs. After that the zone of inhibition was measured.

PREPARATION OF TRANSDERMAL PATCH OF ZNO NANOPARTICLES

Zinc oxide nanoparticles loaded transdermal patch was prepared by using solvent evaporation method [16]. The size of patch was kept as 2*2. For this amount of active ingredient (ZnO NPs), polymer, plasticizer was accurately weighed according to individual formula. Firstly, ZnO NPs was dissolved in methanol. In another beaker 6 ml water was gently heated on water bath. Polymer was gradually added with continuous stirring until the clear solution observed. Then PEG as plasticizer was added with continuous stirring until it gets completely dissolved. Finally, previously prepared ZnO NPs solution was transferred into solution and stirring action continued to obtain appropriate mixture. Solution was cooled and poured into petri plate. Petri plate was kept at room temperature without disturbance for 24 hrs.

Calculation of amount of drug per batch.

$$\frac{(\text{Dose of drug per film} \times \text{Area of petri plate})}{\text{Perbatch dose} = \text{Area of one film}}$$

Dose of drug per film = 10 mg

Area of one film = 4 cm²

Area of petri plate = 65.25 cm

Formulation of Preliminary Batches

Table 1. Formulation of Preliminary Batches.

Ingredient	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5
API	10 mg	10mg	10m	10mg	10mg
PVA	400 mg	-	-	-	-
HPMC E3	-	400mg	-	-	-
HPMC E15	-	-	400mg	-	-
HPMC E5	-	-	-	400mg	-
Sodium alginate	-	-	-	-	400mg
PEG	80mg	80mg	80mg	80mg	80mg
Ethanol	5ml	5ml	5ml	5ml	5ml
Water	10 ml	10ml	10ml	10ml	10ml

EVALUATION OF TRANSDERMAL PATCH.

Weight Variation

Weight variation was studied by individually weighing 3 randomly selected patches. Such determination was performed for each formulation and mean value was calculated [17].

Thickness

Thickness of the patch was measured using digital Vernier callipers at three different places and mean value was calculated.

Folding Endurance

The folding endurance of patch indicates the brittleness and it was measured manually. The patch folded at same side until it breaks or produces visible cracks. To check the ability of patch to withstand folding without breaking was the folding endurance value [18].

IN-VITRO SKIN PERMEATION STUDY

The cellophane membrane side up with an effective diffusion area of 2 cm² were cut and mounted carefully on Franz-type diffusion Cell. The receiver compartments were filled with 15 ml of Physiological saline solution to maintain the sink condition. The diffusion cell apparatus bath temp maintains 37⁰c, with continuous stirring at 100 rpm throughout the experiment. Prepared Trans dermal patch of 2 cm² were mounted on Cellophane membrane. The apparatus fitted with donor compartment. The 5 ml of sample was collected from the medium at predetermined time interval of (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 hrs) and replace with same volume of fresh physiological saline solution. All samples were filtered through a membrane filter and analysed the absorption by using UV- visible spectrophotometry at 374 nm fixed wavelength, calculate the % of drug from patch permeated through skin.

OPTIMIZATION OF FORMULATION

The batch no A4 were selected for optimization. The 2^3 Factorial designs were applied to examine the combined effect of two formulation variables for which batches of ZnO NPs patches were generated. (Table No 5) The amount of HPMC E5 and the amount of PEG were taken as dependable variables and thickness, folding endurance and % drug release were taken as dependent variables. Based on the preliminary feasibility study a DOE with factorial design was performed to optimize HPMC E5 and PEG concentration used in the formulation. The thickness, folding endurance and % drug release of patch was identified as CQA of the formulation composition. The goal of formulation development was to select the optimized HPMC E5 and the amount of PEG concentration and to understand if there was any interaction within the variables. This was used to study the robustness of the proposed formulation by using 2^3 factorial designs of experiments (DOE) [19-21].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

UV-Visible Analysis

The absorbance was measured by using UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 374 nm and the graph was plotted Fig .1. This graph was used for estimation of drug release in the formulated transdermal patch of zinc oxide nanoparticles. The calibration curve which gives correlation coefficient 0.9972.

Fig. 1. UV-Visible spectra of ZnO nanoparticles.

Particle Size Analysis and Antimicrobial Study of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

The histogram of nanoparticle size analysis of ZnO nanoparticles shown in fig.2. The size of ZnO nanoparticles from this analysis resulted in 17.06 nm. Fig.3 and table 2 shows the zone of inhibition of ZnO nanoparticles on *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Aspergillus Niger*, and *Candida albicans*.

Fig. 2. Particle Size Analyser Histogram of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles.

Fig. 3. Zone of inhibition of zinc oxide nanoparticles on (A) *Escherichia coli* (B) *Bacillus subtilis* (C) *Aspergillus niger* (D) *Candida albicans*

Table 2. Zone of inhibition of ZnO NPs.

Microbial strain	Zone of inhibition (mm)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (NCIM 2068)	10
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (NCIM 2655)	7.6
<i>Candida albicans</i> (NCIM 3631)	6
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> (NCIM 1207)	2

Compatibility Study

For the confirmation of interaction of drug in the formulation, the FTIR spectra of Drug Fig.4 and mixture of drug and Excipients Fig.5 were taken and compared. The result revealed that there was no appearance of any extra peaks and disappearance of existing peaks, which indicated that there was no interaction between drug and polymer used.

Fig. 4. FT-IR Spectra of Zinc oxide nanoparticles.

Fig.5 Zinc oxide nanoparticles with HPMC E5.

Evaluation of Preliminary Batches

Table 3 gives the results of Evaluation of preliminary batches for various parameters like weight, thickness, tensile strength, folding endurance and moisture content.

Table 3. Evaluation of Preliminary Batches.

Batch No	Weight (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Tensile Strength (kg/cm ²)	Folding Endurance	Moisture Content (%)
A1	110±2.2	0.321±0.03	0.49±0.08	210	3.3
A2	103±2.3	0.340±0.09	0.33±0.03	225	3.5
A3	109±1.9	0.293±0.05	0.53±0.09	239	2.9
A4	110±1.6	0.312±0.06	0.69±0.04	340	2.1
A5	108±1.8	0.401±0.09	0.32±0.03	180	2.9

In-Vitro Drug Release of Preliminary Batches

The results of *In-Vitro* drug release of all 5 preliminary batches given in table 4.

Table 4. In-Vitro Drug Release of Preliminary Batches.

Time in hrs	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	14	19	34	38	48
2	26	24	48	45	69
4	39	48	59	66	86
6	55	59	74	79	100
8	70	76	88	88	-

Optimization of Formulation

Table 5. Absolute Values of Level of Variables.

Sr. no.	Variables	Level			
	Absolute	Coded	-1	0	+1
1	HPMC E5	X1	300	400	500
2	PEG	X2	60	80	100
	Response		Acceptable Ranges		
3	Thickness (mm)	Y1	NMT 0.35 mm		
4	Folding endurances	Y2	NLT 250 folds		
5	Drug Release (%)	Y3	NLT 100% in 12 hrs		

Table 6. Optimization of Selected A4 Batch.

Ingredient	F1	F 2	F 3	F 4	F 5	F 6	F 7	F 8	F 9	F 10
API	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
HPMC E5	300	400	400	500	500	500	300	400	300	400
PEG	100	80	60	80	100	60	60	80	80	100
Ethanol	5ml									
Water	5ml									

Table 7. Evaluation of Optimized Batches.

Batch No	Weight (mg)	Thickness (mm)	Tensile Strength (kg/cm ²)	Folding Endurance	Moisture Content (%)
F1	103±2.2	0.279±0.03	0.75±0.08	295±5	3.3
F2	111±2.3	0.312±0.09	0.70±0.03	288±6	3.5
F3	109±1.9	0.304±0.05	0.53±0.06	146±2	3.9
F4	146±1.6	0.365±0.06	0.69±0.04	288±5	4.1
F5	160±1.9	0.391±0.03	0.62±0.08	291±6	3.1
F6	151±1.6	0.386±0.03	0.66±0.03	165±4	4.3
F7	186±1.9	0.296±0.03	0.49±0.06	145±8	3.6
F8	103±1.6	0.311±0.03	0.68±0.04	288±2	2.9
F9	109±1.9	0.289±0.03	0.69±0.02	246±3	1.9
F10	111±1.6	0.316±0.03	0.53±0.03	165±4	4.4

Table 8. In-Vitro Drug Release Study of Optimized Batches.

Time (hrs)	% Drug Release									
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	36	40	32	20	14	12	30	35	40	32
2	47	51	48	38	26	26	40	44	53	40
3	56	62	56	43	39	3	53	56	68	56
4	68	76	69	56	40	43	64	68	76	68
5	77	81	76	69	55	59	73	79	84	73
6	89	92	88	74	61	63	88	91	92	88
8	100	100	96	83	69	75	95	100	100	98

FACTORIAL DESIGN

In the 2³ central composite full factorial design the amounts of the HPMC E5 and PEG were chosen as independent variables. A statistical model incorporating factorial terms was used to evaluate the response of variables. The dependable variables of formulation batches D1 to D10 such as thickness in (0.279-0.391) mm, folding endurance in (145-295) folds and drug release in (69-100) % showed a wide variation. The obtained data from DOE trials showed that the dependable variables i.e. DT and wetting time was strongly depending on the selected dependant variables. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to identify insignificant factors. The fig no.6 and 7 illustrates the Counter plot and surface plot, which denotes the combined effects of independent variables on dependent variables. It was observed that the thickness, folding endurance and cumulative drug release were directly proportional to concentration of HPMC E5 and PEG. The observation of factorial design software generated all 10 batches and on the basis of their results the batch F1 was selected as optimised batch.

Fig. 6. Contour Plot.

Fig. 7. 3D Surface Responses.

Stability study:

The optimized formulations F1 stored at $40 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} / 75 \pm 5 \%$ were found stable. After storage at $40 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} / 75 \pm 5 \%$, no shape deformation in the patch was found. The cumulative percentage drug release was nearly similar before and after storage. (Figure No 8.) Therefore, it is clear that drug was thermally stable at $40 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ as well as not affected by high humidity at $75 \pm 5 \%$. Considering the *in vitro* drug release behaviour of optimized formulation of zinc oxide nanoparticle loaded transdermal patch initially and after 1 month, it was found that there was no much more variation in the *in vitro* drug release behaviour of patch.

Fig. 8. Release Mechanism of Optimised Formulation.

Kinetics of Drug Release from Optimised Formulation

The dissolution release data of the optimized formulation D1 was reported and it was fitted in to curve fitting analysis to understand the linear relationship, i.e., kinetic principles. The data were processed for regression analysis using MS - Excel statistical functions. (Table No.9.) The parameters and equations are indicated that the release kinetics of the drug followed Zero-order kinetics from optimized formulation.

Table No.9. Release Mechanism of Optimised Formulation.

Release kinetics	R ² value	Regression equation
Zero-order kinetics	0.9983	$y = 10.964x + 24.714$
First-order kinetics	0.9167	$y = 0.0786x + 1.5$
Hixon-Crowell	0.9879	$y = 0.2325x + 3.1157$
Higuchi Model	0.9891	$y = 40.328x - 9.074$
Korsemeier Peppas's	0.9748	$y = 0.5644x + 1.5079$

CONCLUSION

The objective of this investigation to improve the bioavailability of ZnO NP and maintain the release form patch has been achieved by preparing transdermal patch of zinc oxide nanoparticles by using solvent evaporation method. The results of a 2³ Factorial design revealed that the concentration of polymer and plasticizer are significantly affects on the dependant variables i.e. thickness, folding endurance and % drug release. The optimized batch can be commercialized. It is concluded that by adopting a logical formulation approach an optimum point can be reached in the transdermal patch of zinc oxide nanoparticles by solvent evaporation method, which shows good mechanical strength, and maximum % drug release. It also shows accuracy of dosage form, easy portability and best alternative to liquid dosage form as well as orally administered solid dosage form, i.e. hard gelatine capsules and tablets for paediatric and geriatric patients.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

All Authors declare that they have no conflict of interest

STATEMENT OF HUMAN AND ANIMAL RIGHTS:

This article does not contain any studies with human or animal subjected performed by any of the authors.

Abbreviations

ZnO (Zinc oxide),
NP (Nano particles)

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